

Deviation in days to panicle emergence

Genetics of fertility restoration of wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile lines in rice

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Thirteen elite rice cultivars were crossed with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20 A, IR54752 A, and IR58025 A. Pusa 33, IET6148, Pankaj, Rajshree, and TCA48 were identified as effective restorers based on seed and pollen fertility of the F_1 s.

Only six testcrosses had more than 90% seed and pollen fertility in F_1 . The F_2 progeny of these were analyzed for inheritance of fertility restoration (see

table). On the basis of percent seed set, F_2 plants were grouped as fertile (above 80% seed fertility), partially fertile (20-80% fertility), and sterile (below 20% seed fertility).

Two fertility restoration genes, Rf_1 and Rf_2 , are known in rice. Two independent dominant genes govern seed fertility restoration ability of Pankaj and Rajshree; a single dominant gene governs restoration in Pusa 33.

The mode of action of the two genes varied in the four crosses. The F_2 population of V20 A/Rajshree, IR58025 A/Rajshree, and IR58025 A/Pankaj segregated into a 9-6-1 ratio, revealing epistasis with incomplete dominance. V20 A/Pankaj showed dominant epistasis (12:3:1). V20 A/Pusa 33 and IR58025 A/Pusa 33 showed monogenic segregation (see table).

Segregation for fertility restoration in F_2 populations of some crosses. Cuttack Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 1991 rabi season.

Cross	F_1 seed fertility (%)	F_1 pollen fertility (%)	F_2 plants (no.)	Segregation for seed fertility ^a			Expected segregation ratio	χ^2
				F	PF	S		
V20 A/Rajshree	92	93	154	92	54	8	9:6:1	0.85
V20 A/Pusa 33	92	93	163	116	-	46	3:1	0.99
V20 A/Pankaj	90	91	130	94	26	10	12:3:1	0.67
IR58025 A/Rajshree	91	94	174	101	61	12	9:6:1	0.49
IR58025 A/Pusa 33	94	96	180	142	-	38	3:1	1.45
IR58025 A/Pankaj	92	93	121	72	39	10	9:6:1	1.91

^aF = fertile (above 80% fertility), PF = partially fertile (20-80% fertility); S = sterile (below 20% fertility).

In Pankaj and Rajshree, Rf_1 had a stronger effect on fertility restoration than did Rf_2 . Fertility restoration was high when both dominant alleles (Rf_1 , Rf_2) were present. It was less pronounced when only Rf_1 was present, and was further reduced (partial fertility) when only Rf_2 was present. The double recessive genotype ($rf_1rf_1rf_2rf_2$) did not restore fertility. Only one dominant restorer gene ($RfRf$) was found in Pusa 33.

Variation in seed fertility restoration indicates these genes have different penetrance and are affected by modifiers. ■

Restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile lines derived from MS577 A

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Several stable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (Pushpa A, Mangala A, ES18 A, and Intan Mutant A) developed in Karnataka carry MS577 A cytoplasm and have good agronomic traits. They could not be used directly to develop hybrids, however, because good restorers were not available. We successfully identified effective restorers for them.

We crossed the CMS lines with improved varieties and cultures and obtained 115 F_1 s at the Main Research Station, Hebbal, during 1992 dry season. Hybrids and their parents were transplanted during 1992 wet season in rows of 30 plants spaced at 15 × 20 cm. Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. Three panicles from each plant were marked and then bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains.

Florets from the upper part of the panicles were collected before flowering and stained with 1% acetocarmine for pollen fertility studies. Pollens classified as fertile were fully developed, round, and stained deeply.

Individual plants were classified as fertile, partially fertile, and sterile based on pollen and spikelet fertility. Pollen